

Real Analysis and STACK

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Abstract: We give an overview of how STACK was used in a first-year undergraduate real analysis course at the University of Warwick. We show, through some innovative example questions, how STACK can be adapted to proof-heavy mathematics content. We then present engagement data, performance results and student feedback, which we found to be overwhelmingly positive.

Keywords: Real analysis; Electronic assessments; STACK

1 Introduction

The onset of the Covid-19 pandemic in 2020 urgently forced us to rethink how we assess mathematics at university level. Apart from the fact that handwritten assessments would have to be submitted online, at Warwick we also faced uncertainty in the number of markers, which meant that the number of hand-marked assessments had to be reduced as a contingency measure.

In the summer of 2020, we turned to STACK with the goal of creating self-assessed online quizzes in real analysis that would supplement traditional problem sheets. We wanted to see how far STACK could be used in a heavily proof-based pure mathematics undergraduate course. And thus began the timeline of our STACK implementation:

- Coding phase: June - August 2020
- Testing phase: September - December 2020
- Launch: January to March 2021
- Feedback and data analysis: April 2021

In this work, we will discuss the course syllabus and question creation, highlighting a number of techniques that show how STACK can be used to assess the understanding of analysis proofs. We then discuss the level of student engagement and how well they performed in the quizzes. Finally, we conclude with some reflections what other lecturers teaching pure mathematics courses can learn from our STACK venture.

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2 The *Analysis II* module

We worked on *Analysis II* - a core module for first-year mathematics undergraduates at Warwick. The intake was about 400. This is second course in real analysis follows from the foundation in numbers, sequences and series in *Analysis I*. Teaching materials, including online quizzes, were to be created on the *Moodle* virtual learning environment.

Here is the weekly scope of the course given over 10 weeks.

1. ε - δ definition of continuity
2. Sequential definition of continuity
3. Continuity on an interval, Intermediate Value Theorem
4. Limits
5. Inverse Function Theorem
6. Differentiation, Carathéodory's theorem
7. Mean Value Theorem, L'Hôpital's Rule
8. Taylor's Theorem, Lagrange form of the remainder
9. Radius of convergence
10. Differentiation of power series

Our goal was to create one set of STACK assessment for each week's material. Each set should take around 30-40 minutes to complete.

3 Rubric

In the previous year, students had to submit 9 problem sheets, one in each week (except week 10). However, Covid-related uncertainties meant that we had to cut this number down to only 4 problem sheets, which counted for 10% of the final grade.

To supplement the above, we created 11 sets of STACK quizzes, two of which were not counted (one on syntax training, and one on *Analysis I* revision). They were practice quizzes, in the sense that students could do them an unlimited number of times before the deadline, each attempt building on the last. Each quiz had a pass mark of around 85% (not uniform across the quizzes). Passing 6 out of 9 quizzes gave the student a flat 5% for the module.

We used STACK to create over 40 multi-part questions over 4 weeks. We are grateful for George Kinnear's talk on *JSXGraph* at previous STACK conferences, and for the talk and paper by Robbie Bickerton and Chris Sangwin [BJ21], both of whom gave us inspirations to apply their scaffolding and proof-comprehension techniques to *Analysis II*.

4 Question highlights

Here we highlight some techniques used, along with the screenshots of the quizzes. See Figs 1-5. (The large pink texts in the figures are not part of the published quizzes.)

JSXgraph + Slider. (Fig. 1) This question allows the ϵ - δ definition of continuity at a point $c \in \mathbb{R}$ to be visualised in an interactive way. The point c can be moved with a mouse, and the slider can be used to adjust the value of ϵ , with a readout for a viable value of δ .

Fig. 1: JSXgraph + Slider. The ϵ - δ continuity is visualised in an interactive way.

JSXgraph + Zoom. (Fig. 2) This question concerns an interesting counterexample in analysis in which a function (graph shown in blue) satisfies $f'(0) > 0$, but is not strictly increasing near the origin. Intuitively, this is because the function becomes increasingly 'wiggly' near the origin. Students can discover this by using the zoom function of JSXgraph. The question is followed up with a rigorous fill-in-the-blank proof of this property.

Tidy STACK question tool | Question tests & deployed variants

We are going to study a function, $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, with the following strange property:

f is differentiable at $c \in \mathbb{R}$ and $f'(c) > 0$, yet there exists no neighbourhood of c in which f is strictly increasing.

(You should find this somewhat disturbing.)

One function with this property is:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x + 2x^2 \sin\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) & x \neq 0 \\ 0 & x = 0 \end{cases}$$

The above graph shows the function $y = f(x)$ (the blue curve), which is bounded between the upper (red) curve and the lower (green) curve. (Try the zoom in/out and shift buttons.)

JSXgraph zoom

Give the equations of the red and green curves.

Red: $y =$

Green: $y =$

Now we will show that the function f satisfies the strange property.

We start by proving that $f'(0) > 0$.

From the definition of a derivative,

$$f'(0) = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x) - f(0)}{x - 0}$$

$$= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{?+?*\sin(1/x)}{x} \right)$$

Syntax hints

= a number .

In the last step, we use the fact that $-2x \leq 2x \sin\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) \leq 2x$, and let $x \rightarrow 0$ and apply the theorem.

2i) We now prove that f is not locally increasing at $x = 0$.

2i) f is locally increasing at 0 iff $\forall \delta > 0$, ≥ 0 in $(-\delta, \delta)$.

2ii) Hence, it suffices to show that $\exists c \in (-\delta, \delta)$ such that .

2iii) Now,

$$f'(x) = \begin{cases} ? & x \neq 0 \\ 1 & x = 0 \end{cases}$$

Fill in the missing derivative.

2iv) By the property of real numbers, $\forall \delta > 0, \exists n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $0 < \frac{1}{n} < 2\pi\delta$.

2v) Let $c = \frac{1}{2\pi n} \in (0, \delta)$. Then $f'(c) =$.

Hence, the function f indeed satisfies our counterintuitive property.

This is one reason why analysis is so important: our intuition can be misleading!

Fig. 2: JSXgraph + Zoom. The surprising property of a function around $x = 0$ is rigorously studied.

Recall the following from school mathematics:

Drag and drop onto jpg

The Chain Rule: Let $g: I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $f: J \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, where I and J are intervals, and $f(J) \subseteq I$. Let $c \in J$. Suppose f is differentiable at c and g is differentiable at $d = f(c)$, then the composition $g \circ f$ is differentiable at c with

$$(g \circ f)'(c) = g'(d) \cdot f'(c).$$

In the picture below, drag the following objects into the correct positions to give a visualisation of the function composition in the Chain Rule. (This will help us with the proof below.)

[Hint: Blue= Set, Pink= Function, Orange= Number]

g d J f o g g o f I f c

Fig. 3: Drag and drop. Function composition is visualised and complicated notation clarified.

We will now prove the Chain Rule using Carathéodory's Theorem.

a) Fill in the blanks in the proof below.

Fill in the blanks

Proof:

1) Since f is differentiable at c , $\exists \varphi_1: J \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, continuous at c , such that $\forall x \in J$, $f(x) - f(c) =$

 and $f'(c) =$.

2) Since g is differentiable at d , $\exists \varphi_2: I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, continuous at d , such that $\forall y \in I$, $g(y) - g(d) =$

 and $g'(d) =$.

3) Let $y = f(x)$. Then

$$g(f(x)) - g(f(c)) = \varphi_2(f(x)) \cdot [f(x) - f(c)]$$

and so $g \circ f(x) - g \circ f(c) = \varphi_2 \circ f(x) \cdot$.

4) Hence, where $\varphi(x) = \varphi_2 \circ f(x) \cdot \varphi_1(x)$, we know that φ is continuous at c and so $g \circ f$ is differentiable at c .

5) We therefore have $(g \circ f)'(c) = \varphi'(c) = \varphi_2 \circ f(c) \cdot$ $= g'(d) \cdot f'(c)$.

Further questions:

Proof comprehension

b) Which of the above steps is a consequence of Carathéodory's Theorem?

c) Which step of the proof is a consequence of the Algebra of Continuous Functions?

Fig. 4: A typical STACK scaffolded proof, with proof comprehension, following on from the previous drag-and-drop question.

Drag and Drop. We found it useful to mix STACK with Moodle-type questions. In this example, the drag-and-drop type (Fig. 3) is used to visualise function composition and clarify the otherwise complicated notation. The follow-up question (Fig. 4) concerns the proof of the Chain Rule using Carathéodory's Theorem. We implemented this in STACK with scaffolded proofs and proof comprehension.

Ordering. (See Fig. 5) This Moodle-type question asks students to reconstruct a proof of a property of the exponential function by re-ordering jumbled up statements into a logical order. This reinforces the point that statements regarding rational numbers can be proved first for integers, then reciprocals then rationals in that order.

Place the following statements in the correct order to prove that $\forall r \in \mathbb{Q}$

$E(r) = e^r,$

Ordering

where the constant $e \equiv E(1)$.

Thus $E(r) = e^r$ holds for all $r = \pm \frac{m}{n}$ where $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$.

$E\left(-\frac{m}{n}\right) = \frac{1}{E(m/n)} = \frac{1}{e^{\frac{m}{n}}} = e^{-\frac{m}{n}}.$

using the property $E(x + y) = E(x) \cdot E(y)$ inductively.

Consequently, $E\left(\frac{1}{n}\right) = [E(1)]^{\frac{1}{n}} \implies E(r) = e^r$. Once again, the relation holds.

If $r \in \mathbb{Z}$, $E(r) = E(1 + 1 + \dots + 1) = E(1) \cdot E(1) \cdot \dots \cdot E(1)$,

Hence, the relation $E(r) = (E(1))^r = e^r$ for all $r \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Hence, $E(1) = \left[E\left(\frac{1}{n}\right)\right]^n.$

Hence, $E(r) = \left[E\left(\frac{1}{n}\right)\right]^m = \left(e^{\frac{1}{n}}\right)^m = e^{\frac{m}{n}} = e^r$, and the relation also holds in this case.

If $r = \frac{m}{n}$ where $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, then $E(r) = E\left(\frac{m}{n}\right) = E\left(\frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{n} + \dots + \frac{1}{n}\right).$

If $r = -\frac{m}{n}$ where $m, n \in \mathbb{N}$, we use the property $E(-x) = 1/E(x)$ to deduce that

If $r = \frac{1}{n}$ where $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we have $E(1) = E\left(n \cdot \frac{1}{n}\right) = E\left(\frac{1}{n} + \frac{1}{n} + \dots + \frac{1}{n}\right).$

Combining these results with the fact that $E(0) = 1 = e^0$, the property $E(r) = e^r$ holds for all $r \in \mathbb{Q}$.

Fig. 5: Ordering. A property of the exponential function is to be proved by reordering proof fragments into a logical order.

5 Results

We now discuss the data obtained after the course concluded.

Average vs. pass marks. Fig. 6 shows the average final marks (top line) versus the pass marks (bottom line) for the quizzes in weeks 1 to 9. We see that students achieved marks of around 90-95%, comfortably above the pass marks. Peaks and troughs on the top line correlate to the difficulty of each quiz (this was confirmed by studying the mark distributions in the ‘peak’ and ‘trough’ weeks). This data can be used to adjust the difficulty next year.

How many attempts? In Fig. 7, the top panel shows the total number of attempts per week. The drop off towards the end may be due to the fact that, for those who had already achieved the required number of passes, they did not feel the need to submit as many attempts. The bottom panel shows the average number of attempts per student (between 2.3-3.3), although there were students who submitted many more than 2 attempts (including even those who passed the first time!). This is evidence for a high level of engagement with the quizzes.

Fig. 6: The top line shows the average marks that student achieved, which are comfortably above the pass marks. These are plotted against week number. The peaks and troughs in the top curve correlate with the difficulty of each quiz.

Fig. 7: Top: The total number of attempts per week. Bottom: The *average* number of attempts per week. These data suggest a high level of engagement with the quizzes.

Safety net?. Although only 6 out of 9 passes are required for a flat 5%, Fig. 8 shows that around half of all students passed all 9 quizzes. Over 90% of students passed overall. We note that deadline extensions and mitigations have not been taken into account, so the final data may even show stronger engagement. This goes to show that the material in the quizzes are engaging enough for most students not to rely on the 6-out-of-9 safety net.

Fig. 8: The pie chart shows that around half of all students passed all 9 quizzes.

6 Student feedback

When asked: “*Apart from the lecture notes and videos, what other resources are useful for the understanding of Analysis II?*”, we found that 88% of respondents rated the quizzes as useful. As many students rated the problem sheets as useful. This is evidence that when implemented properly, the learning gains from STACK quizzes are comparable to those of traditional pen-and-paper assignments.

When asked to “*Name one thing about the module which has had the most impact on your learning in this course*”, a number of students thought the STACK quizzes were the most impactful element of the course. Some comments include:

“The quizzes were helpful and the infinite attempts ensured that I did not feel pressured while doing them, allowing me to focus on understanding the content.”

“The quizzes have been a very useful interactive learning tool.”

“The alternating assessment format between quizzes and written assignments is nice and helped reduce stress.”

In fact, the success of the STACK quizzes helped this module achieve the ‘best first-year mathematics module’ accolade.

7 Reflections

Proofs work well as quizzes: We found that a lot of lecture time was saved by fashioning proofs into STACK quizzes. This is important considering that in the present academic year, students are generally overwhelmed by the amount of video lectures to watch. The interactivity in the STACK quizzes also meant that students understood the proofs much more clearly than when the proofs were recited during lectures.

Beta-test on students and lecturers: It is essential to have a more experienced pair of eyes to test the quizzes. We found that lecturers could pick up subtle errors that were not spotted by a large pool of student beta testers.

Post-deadline practice: Remember to duplicate quizzes so that students can go back and reattempt the quizzes after the deadlines, without having one attempt building on the last. This is useful during exam revision, and also for those who did not engage with the quizzes the first time round.

8 Conclusions

STACK can be successfully applied to a wide range of mathematics content, including pure mathematics at university level as our work has demonstrated. We have shown that it is possible to turn proofs in existing lecture notes and problem sheets into interactive online quizzes, even in pure proof-heavy courses like ours.

STACK was the primary tool for question creation, although we also found it useful to mix STACK with other native Moodle-type questions for a varied diet. Creating questions on STACK is an ideal co-creation project which can be done as a summer internship. There are long-term benefits for everyone involved.

To our delight, we found that students found STACK quizzes to be as useful as doing traditional problem sheets. However, we emphasise that good online quizzes require a considerable amount of time investment in the creation and testing (in our case, over a period of 6 months). Sloppily made online quizzes can easily become a frustrating obstacle to learning mathematics. Nevertheless, despite the time and effort required, the rewards are to be reaped in the long term year after year.

Bibliography

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